

ANALYSING MATERIALS (COURSEBOOKS, LESSON PLANS, ACTIVITIES) FOR TEACHING INTERCULTURAL ISSUES.

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Abstract: Understanding the nature of the relationship between language and culture is central to the process of learning and teaching another language. In actual language use, it is not the case that it is only the forms of language that convey meaning. It is language in its cultural context that creates meaning: creating and interpreting meaning is done within a cultural framework. In language learning classrooms, learners need to engage with the ways in which context affects what is communicated and how. Both the learner's culture and the culture in which meaning is created or communicated have an influence on the ways in which possible meanings are understood. This study aimed to investigate the impact of culture in teaching and learning English as a foreign language and also it suggests some ways of how to teach culture in classroom.

Keywords: Culture, Language, English as a foreign language

INTRODUCTION

The culture of people, in its broad sense, refers to all aspects of shared life in community. We are growing up in a social group learn ways of looking at things, doing things, expressing things and solving certain problems in certain ways. We also learn to value something and despise or avoid other things. These attitudes, reactions and emotions become part of our ways of life without being conscious of them. Yet these culturally determined features actually have rooted in a deeper and more significant social conventions,

relations and assumptions which are composed of the main stream of a culture of a people. A language is learned and used within such a context, drawing from the culture distinctive meanings and functions which must be assimilated by language learners if they are to control the languages as native speakers control it.

Goals for culture teaching

Culture teaching is a long and complex process concerning something more than language use itself. In doing the above activities, the aim is to increase students' awareness and to develop their curiosity towards the target culture and their own, helping them to make comparisons among cultures. The comparisons are not meant to underestimate any of the cultures being analyzed, but to enrich students' experience and to make them aware that although some culture elements are being globalized, there is still diversity among cultures. This diversity should then be understood, and never underestimated. Then where should we go and what to achieve in this field is the next important lesson to deal with. Several goals are thus proposed by Seelye in which student are supposed to demonstrate that they have acquired certain understandings, abilities, and attitudes:

That they can demonstrate¹ how people conventionally act in the most common mundane and crisis situations in the target language;

That they are able to evaluate the relative strength of a generality concerning

1 Demonstrate - give a practical exhibition and explanation of (how a machine, skill, or craft works or is performed).

the target culture in terms of the amount of evidence substantiating the statement;

That they have developed the skills needed to locate and organize material about the target culture from the library, mass media, and personal observation;

That they understand that such social variables as age, sex, social class, and the place of residence affect the way people speak and behave.

The interrelationship between language and culture

Language and culture are so close that are being identified as synonyms (Scarcella, Oxford, 1992). On the one hand, language is used to express people's cultural thoughts, beliefs and to communicate; on the other hand, culture is embedded in the language. The interwoven relationship between language and culture can be summarized by Brown (2000, p.177): "A language is a part of a culture and a culture is a part of a language; the two are intricately interwoven so that one cannot separate the two without losing the significance of either language or culture.

Language, culture and communication

Both of language and culture have a function of communication because they both carry meanings. On the one hand, language carries syntactic, semantic and pragmatic meanings for language users to communicate (Brooks, 1997). On the other hand, culture carries meanings and cultural meanings are expressed through patterns of behaviour, e.g., language. In order to communicate successfully across languages and cultures, one must understand culturally different norms of interaction and people's values and thought (Saville-Troike, 2003). Sometimes linguistic correct sentences could cause misunderstanding or confusion when they are in a different cultural context (Schulz, 2007).

CULTURE TEACHING HISTORY

THE INTERCULTURAL DIMENSION

Knowledge of cultures is important for facilitating communication with people. Therefore learners of languages need to learn about and understand cultures. Understanding culture as practices with which people engage becomes centrally important. This means that in the language classroom it is not just a question of learners developing knowledge about another culture but of learners coming to understand themselves in relation to some other culture. This is why there is a contemporary emphasis on ‘intercultural’. Learning to be intercultural involves much more than just knowing about another culture: it involves learning to understand how one’s own culture shapes perceptions of oneself, of the world, and of our relationship with others. Learners need to become familiar with how they can personally engage with linguistic and cultural diversity.

There is another way to think about culture in language teaching: the distinction between a cultural perspective and an intercultural perspective (Liddicoat, 2005).

This ‘cultural’ pole implies the development of knowledge about culture which remains external to the learner and is not intended to confront or transform the learner’s existing identity, practices, values, attitudes, beliefs and worldview. The ‘intercultural’ pole implies the transformational engagement of the learner in the act of learning.

Taking an intercultural perspective in language teaching and learning involves more than developing knowledge of other people and places. It means learning that all human beings are shaped by their cultures and that communicating across cultures involves accepting both one’s own culturally conditioned nature and that of others and the ways in which these are at play in communication.

Learning another language can be like placing a mirror up to one’s own culture and one’s own assumptions about how communication happens, what

particular messages mean and what assumptions³ one makes in one's daily life. Effective intercultural learning therefore occurs as the student engages in the relationships between the cultures that are at play in the language classroom. Such learning involves much more than just developing knowledge about some other culture and its language.

The intercultural framework proposed here, then, consists of three intersecting dimensions for understanding approaches to the teaching of culture in language learning:

- The nature of content: artifact -practice
- The nature of learning: fact-process
- The nature of the educational effect: cultural-intercultural.

In learning about culture in the language classroom, we need to draw on our own experiences of language and culture as they are encountered when trying to create and interpret meanings.

The ability to learn beyond the classroom is probably more important than any particular information that students may learn about another culture during their schooling. This is because it is impossible to teach *all* of any culture because cultures are variable and diverse. As languages educators, we know that what we can teach in the classroom is inevitably only a partial picture of a language and culture. By acknowledging that limitation in our own teaching, we are less likely to develop stereotypical views of the cultures we are teaching about. Learning how to learn about culture means that, as people engage with new aspects of culture, they develop their knowledge and awareness and find ways of acting according to their new learning.

One way of developing intercultural capabilities is through an interconnected set of activities involving:

- noticing cultural similarities and differences as they are made evident through language

- comparing what one has noticed about another language and culture with what one already knows about other languages and cultures
- reflecting on what one's experience of linguistic and cultural diversity means for oneself.

How one reacts to diversity, how one thinks about diversity, how one feels about diversity and how one will find ways of engaging constructively.

CULTURE TEACHING DEVICES

Dialogues and mini-dramas

Usually, in a conventional teacher-student situation, students feel foolish if asked to respond in a foreign way with an accurate imitation of the sounds of the language and with appropriate gestures. In this case, situations are proposed which students then act out in a culturally authentic fashion, a common method used in language teaching called dialogue or mini-drama. Each dialogue should be constructed around an experience compatible with the age and interests of the students. As students become familiar with the dialogue and act it out, they can learn through role playing how to interact with all kinds of people, as they did in their own culture. Such experience is valuable more than many lines of comment and explanation. In terms of the material, some textbooks deliberately began with dialogues reflecting common and everyday experience of the students in their native culture. But acting out dialogues of this type confirms the impression of many students that the new language is the native language in a new address which students are very familiar with in any case. In other textbooks, one finds the dialogues are deliberately kept "culturally neutral" which will be inevitably interpreted by the students as familiar patterns of their own cultures. The two cases are, to some degree, deprive the students from being exposed to the real situation, and thus should be avoided. So authenticity of situational material is extremely valuable as the dialogue or drama reading faithfully reflects the behaviors in the target culture.

